

A SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW ON CLIMATE MODELING, CHALLENGES AND UNCERTAINTIES

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ABSTRACT

In order to comprehend and forecast the Earth's climate system, climate modeling has become an essential tool. This review study focuses on climate modeling in sustainable development, challenges and uncertainties by reviewing twenty five (25) research papers since 2006 to 2024 filtered from several academic databases (ScienceDirect, ResearchGate, Springer). The strategy of the study was to narrow the results using key words "climate predictions", "model uncertainties", and "climate modeling". The chosen papers underwent a comprehensive analysis to identify emerging trends, recent advancements, challenges, and opportunities during the course of the 18 year period. The review examines different kinds of climate models, from basic energy balance models to intricate Earth system models, and discuss about how they are used to investigate the dynamics and give insights into how the application of climate prediction data in identifying hydrological trends, temperature and precipitation extremes under different climate scenarios while providing a thorough review of the benefits and drawbacks of climate modeling. Complex climatic processes including cloud formation, ocean-atmosphere interactions, and feedback mechanisms are typically difficult for these models to adequately simulate. Furthermore, it's possible that model resolution is too low to precisely depict regional climatic changes and extreme weather occurrences. Projections are further complicated by uncertainties regarding land-use changes, greenhouse gas emissions, and future socioeconomic trends. Ultimately leading to more accurate and consistent climate projections by identifying present gaps and future research objectives, this paper supports the policy decisions which may guide the researchers, decision-makers, and practitioners.

Keywords: Climate adaptation; Climate modeling; Model uncertainties; Sustainable development.

MỘT ĐÁNH GIÁ HỌC THUẬT CÓ TÍNH HỆ THỐNG VỀ MÔ HÌNH HOÁ KHÍ HẬU, CÁC THÁCH THỨC VÀ NHỮNG BẤT ỔN

Tóm tắt

Để hiểu và dự báo hệ thống khí hậu của Trái đất, mô hình khí hậu đã trở thành một công cụ thiết yếu. Nghiên cứu đánh giá này tập trung vào mô hình khí hậu trong phát triển bền vững, những thách thức và bất ổn bằng cách phân tích tổng hợp hai mươi lăm (25) bài báo nghiên cứu từ năm 2006 đến năm 2024 được lọc từ một số cơ sở dữ liệu học thuật (ScienceDirect, ResearchGate, Springer). Mục đích của nghiên cứu là thu hẹp kết quả bằng cách sử dụng các từ khóa "dự đoán khí hậu", "bất ổn mô hình" và "mô hình khí hậu". Các bài báo được chọn đã trải qua quá trình phân tích toàn diện để xác định các xu hướng mới nổi, những tiến bộ gần đây, thách thức và cơ hội trong suốt giai đoạn 18 năm. Đánh giá này xem xét các loại mô hình khí hậu khác nhau, từ các mô hình cân bằng năng lượng cơ bản đến các mô hình hệ thống Trái đất phức tạp và thảo luận về cách chúng được sử dụng để điều tra động lực học và đưa ra hiểu biết sâu sắc về cách ứng dụng dữ liệu dự báo khí hậu trong việc xác định xu hướng thủy văn, nhiệt độ và lượng mưa

cực đoan trong các kịch bản khí hậu khác nhau, đồng thời cung cấp đánh giá kỹ lưỡng về những lợi ích và hạn chế của mô hình khí hậu. Các quá trình khí hậu phức tạp bao gồm sự hình thành mây, tương tác đại dương-khí quyển và cơ chế phản hồi thường khó để các mô hình này mô phỏng đầy đủ. Hơn nữa, có thể độ phân giải mô hình quá thấp để mô tả chính xác những thay đổi khí hậu khu vực và các hiện tượng thời tiết khắc nghiệt. Các dự báo còn phức tạp hơn nữa do những bất ổn liên quan đến thay đổi sử dụng đất, phát thải khí nhà kính và xu hướng kinh tế xã hội trong tương lai. Cuối cùng dẫn đến các dự báo khí hậu chính xác và nhất quán hơn bằng cách xác định các khoảng cách hiện tại và các mục tiêu nghiên cứu trong tương lai, bài báo này hỗ trợ các quyết định chính sách có thể hướng dẫn các nhà nghiên cứu, người ra quyết định và người thực hành.

Từ khóa: Thích ứng khí hậu; Mô hình khí hậu; Độ không đảm bảo của mô hình; Bền vững; phát triển

1. INTRODUCTION

The greatest threat to our planet in the twenty-first century is climate change. With the start of the industrial revolution, the problem of global climate grew exponentially (Abbass et al., 2022). It has an impact on every aspect of the sustainable development process, including the environment, society, and economy (Wang et al., 2023). An increasing number of ecological and environmental issues have arisen as a result of surface environmental changes, resource depletion, climate change, and other reasons (Yan et al., 2023). Drought, an excessive temperature, land salinization, and the disruption of terrestrial and marine

ecosystems are some examples of these. These factors can lead to environmental risks, including those involving agricultural productivity, food supply, air pollution, infrastructure and resource degradation, and financial loss and damage. Furthermore, it could take months or even years following the disaster for there to be additional significant financial losses, including lost business revenue or job losses (Chen et al., 2023).

The process of achieving the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) indicators will be facilitated by the integration of climate change in the sustainable development management

strategies (Oleru et al., 2021). The relationship between climate change and sustainable development, particularly in light of climate change, has not, however, been thoroughly studied quantitatively.

Climate models are essential in attempting to comprehend the intricate relationship between climate change and the SDGs from the perspectives of climate change and multiple development scenarios. It is also important to investigate how the SDGs have changed over time to uncover the relationship between how various climate indicators respond to sustainable development, which helps to promote a better understanding of how climate change impacts ecosystems and enhances their well-being. The outcomes of future climate modeling can

be utilized by regional managers to create development plans that work for the here and now.

This review explores the (a) climate modeling in sustainable development, (b) challenges and uncertainties. Furthermore, the paper serves as a comprehensive guide for researchers, policymakers, and practitioners, providing insights into the dynamic intersection of climate modeling for a sustainable future.

2. METHODOLOGY

A rigorous and comprehensive review approach was used to deeply review the recent applications and advancements of climate modeling to achieve climate

Table 1 Types of Climate Models and their general functions

Classification	Models	General functions	Reference
Thermodynamic model	Energy Balance Models	Generate a space-time average of the Earth's surface temperature	North & Stevens, 2006
	Radiative-Convective Models	Compute the vertical distribution of globally and seasonally averaged surface and atmospheric temperatures	Labarre et al., 2019
		(horizontal dynamics are ignored in these models)	
Hydrodynamic model /General Circulation Models (GCMs)	Atmospheric General Circulation Models	Weather forecasting (typically 3-10 days) Seasonal forecasting (typically 3-12 months)	Teixeira et al., 2014
	Ocean General Circulation Models	Simulate the interactions between oceans and other components of the climate system at variable temporal and spatial scales. Investigate different physical processes, including turbulent eddies in oceanic-mid-latitudes, meridional heat fluxes, thermohaline circulation, and the general circulation of tropical oceans.	Yoon & Ma, 2012
	Coupled Atmospheric-Ocean General Circulation Models	Simulate complex interactions between the four main climate system components (land, atmosphere, sea ice, and ocean) over time.	Tehrani et al., 2022

adaptability and environmental sustainability. The procedure began with a thorough search of several academic databases (ScienceDirect, ResearchGate, Springer) and this comprehensive search included the use of pertinent keywords including "sustainability", "model uncertainties" and "climate modeling" to find a variety of research articles, and papers that provided insight into the topic (Madushanka et al., 2024). This study included reviewing scientific communications published between 2006 and 2024. To determine its applicability to the subject, the calibre of the methodology used, and the veracity of the results reported, the chosen literature went through a thorough screening procedure. Accordingly, 25 research articles were filtered out of the chosen articles (Nawarathna et al., 2024). After that, data

extraction was carried out in order to distinguish and extract important findings that addressed the most important aspects of climate modeling. Furthermore, the technique utilized in this study covered more than basic data analysis; it also included a critical review of the merits and downsides of previous research as well as future research potential, ensuring a thorough and well-informed approach (Peiris et al., 2024).

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Climate modeling

Climate modeling is the application of mathematical or software-based approaches to replicate the various interactions that occur in the environment between air, water, and land.

Table 2 Recent applications of climate modeling

Type of model	Role of model	Location and the time period of the study	Reference
Integrated valuation of ecosystem services and tradeoffs (InVEST)	Simulated and analyzed the spatiotemporal variations and the impacts of Climate and land use/land cover and climate changes on water yield from.	2001-2019 in the upstream regions of the Shule River Basin on the northeastern margin of the Qinghai-Tibet Plateau	Wei et al., 2021
Directional unit hydrograph model	Assessing the effect of storm structure and velocity on hydrograph response. This model simplifies storm fields into rectangular moving storms, incorporating storm shape, speed, and direction into the instantaneous unit hydrograph function.	2002-2020 in Turkey River watershed in Iowa State, USA, an agricultural watershed, with a drainage area of 4385 km ²	Perez et al., 2023
GCM RCP 4.5 and 8.5	Used to project future climate changes	1981-2016 in Tugwi Mukosi dam sub-catchment area in Zimbabwe	Dzirekwa et al., 2023
Australian water resources assessment landscape model	The model observes river streamflow, satellite soil moisture, and evapotranspiration across the continent. It reproduces historical hydrological trends and prepares historical reference simulations using observed climate inputs. Evaluated against hydrological observations, it performs well for various water balance variables at observation sites.	1976-2005 in Australian continent	Vogel et al., 2023
Coupled model inter-comparison project phase 6 models	Utilized to evaluate the impact of climate change on global solar radiation in the region.	Alberta province, Canada	Eum et al., 2023
GCM-CanESM	Used for novel science applications such as generating large initial condition ensembles for detection and attribution.	1981-2016 in Tugwi Mukosi dam sub-catchment area in Zimbabwe	Dzirekwa et al., 2023; Swart et al., 2019
Urban flood model	Studying the impact of direct and indirect connections between urban systems, explore their relative importance in the network, and prioritize related risks to improve resource allocation efficiency.	1981-2016 Tugwi Mukosi dam sub-catchment area in Zimbabwe	Dzirekwa et al., 2023
CanRCM4-LE model	Used to generate a 50-member large ensemble simulation for the historical (1950-2005) and future (2006-2100) periods under the Regional Concentration Pathway (RCP) 8.5 scenario. Also employed to assess the projected changes of joint temperature and precipitation extremes over Canada using the large ensemble simulations. The study assesses the impact of climate change on temperature and precipitation extremes across different seasons and spatial scales within Canada.	The research area of the study is focused on Canada, specifically examining the projected changes in joint temperature and precipitation extremes over the country.	Singh et al., 2022

Changing one or more of the variables in the model will result in a change (Hoyle, 2024). Table 1 explains types of climate models and their general functions.

Numerical climate models, while having limitations, are useful for understanding atmospheric processes, studying Earth system interconnections, and simulating past and future climates (Hostetler, 2015) as given in Table 2.

3.2. Advantages of Climate models

Climate modeling offers several important advantages that significantly contribute to our understanding of the Earth's climate system. One of the primary benefits is the ability to predict future climate conditions by simulating the interactions between various components of the climate system, including the atmosphere, oceans, and land surfaces. This potential to predict is crucial for preparing for and mitigating the impacts of climate change. Additionally, climate models enable scientists to test hypotheses about the climate system's behavior and explore the potential outcomes of different scenarios, such as varying levels of greenhouse gas emissions. This helps in formulating effective policies and strategies for climate action. Furthermore, climate models are invaluable in identifying and understanding complex climate processes and feedback mechanisms that are difficult to observe directly. By integrating vast amounts of observational data and theoretical knowledge, these models provide a comprehensive image of past, present, and future climate conditions, thereby enhancing our ability to make informed decisions aimed at safeguarding the environment and human societies.

3.3. Challenges and uncertainties of climate modelling

Following studies have been carried on regarding the common uncertainties and uncertainty modeling methods for long-term sustainable planning (Feng et al., 2023). Uncertainties about the climatic effects of artificial aerosols are major drawback in quantitative attribution studies and attempts to use the observational record to constrain climate sensitivity. There is no clear clue on exact amount of warming caused

by greenhouse gases has been offset by aerosol-induced cooling. Cloud uncertainties complicate predicting the climatic effects of aerosols since these aerosols interact with clouds and have the ability to affect cloud radiative characteristics and cloud cover (Bader et al., 2008).

Model projections are fundamentally unreliable since no model can fully describe the system it purports to specify. All models are faulty to some degree. Uncertainty in model projections is caused by boundary and initial condition uncertainty, an incomplete theoretical understanding of the system, parameter uncertainty, and the fact that our models are flawed (Stainforth et al., 2007). Current models do not always represent regional patterns in extreme occurrences, making it difficult to judge the significance of these inconsistencies and discern between model flaws and natural variability. The quality of simulations of low-frequency

variability on decadal to multi-decadal time spans varies both geographically and between models. On average, models perform well in the North Pacific and North Atlantic. In other oceanic locations, a paucity of data adds to uncertainty in determining simulation quality at low frequencies (Bader et al., 2008).

There is no sufficient information about some processes to replicate them using a model. To sample these uncertainties, numerous empirical parametrizations of the same process are available. The observational evidence does not always constrain the parameter values employed in these parametrizations, resulting in parameter uncertainty. All existing climate models are acknowledged to be empirically insufficient, meaning that no set of parameters can always fit the observations within their uncertainties. This is commonly known as structural error (Knutti, 2008). In addition to computational constraints limiting model resolution, create limitations in the model that are frequently persistent for whatever set of parameters chosen (Sanderson et al., 2008).

3.4. Future directions and opportunities

Climate modeling's future prospects and directions are centered on enhancing resolution,

accuracy, and the integration of many data sources. Higher-resolution models that more accurately represent local climate changes and extreme weather events will be possible because to advancements in computing capacity (Olaleru et al., 2021). Another major goal is to improve the representations of intricate processes like cloud dynamics and carbon cycle feedbacks. Machine learning and artificial intelligence together can improve data assimilation and model predictions. Furthermore, improved inter-disciplinary cooperation as well as a larger utilization of satellite and other observational data would improve the validity and dependability of models (Yan et al., 2023). These developments will help policymakers better address the difficulties posed by climate change by giving them more accurate and useful insights.

4. CONCLUSION

One of the most significant risks of global stability in the twenty-first century is climate change, which affects the environmental, social, and economic aspects of sustainable development. This study emphasized the crucial role of climate modeling for expanding the understanding of climate change and aiding sustainable development efforts. When results

from many studies are combined, it is clear that climate models are essential resources for forecasting future climate scenarios, evaluating the effects on ecosystems and human societies, and developing adaptive measures. The range of models covered, including General Circulation Models (GCMs) and Energy Balance Models, highlights how adaptable these models are at replicating intricate interactions within the Earth's climate system. Specific models discussed in the paper include the Integrated Valuation of Ecosystem Services and Tradeoffs (InVEST), GCM RCP 4.5 and 8.5 are employed to project future climate changes in their study areas while the Australian water resources assessment landscape model evaluates hydrological trends. Additionally, the CanRCM4-LE model have been used to examining temperature and precipitation extremes under different climate scenarios. These models underscore the diverse applications of climate modeling in studying regional and global climate impacts, informing policy decisions,

and enhancing understanding of environmental dynamics.

Nevertheless, the study recognizes the major challenges and uncertainties that come with modeling the climate. Aerosol-cloud interactions, parameter uncertainty, and structural constraints in model representation are some of the issues that highlight the continuous need for enhancements and validation with observational data. By addressing these issues, model projections will become more accurate and reliable, which will increase their usefulness in directing successful climate policy and adaptation plans. It is recommended that future research concentrate on expanding interdisciplinary cooperation, boosting geographical specificity, integrating new data sources, and refining model capabilities. These initiatives are essential to the advancement of climate science and the maintenance of the crucial role that climate models will play in determining our planet's sustainable future. Climate modeling involves enhancing resolution, accuracy, and data integration. Advancements in computing capacity will enable higher-resolution models, improving representations of complex processes like cloud dynamics and carbon cycle feedbacks. Machine learning and artificial intelligence will enhance data assimilation and model predictions, aiding scholars, decision-makers, and practitioners, in addressing climate change challenges. It promotes a deeper knowledge of how these techniques might help address the biggest concerns of today, including mitigation and adaptation to climate change, by shedding light on the potentials and limitations of climate modeling. □

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